

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Running a Kaggle Competition

Organizing a code development competition on Google's Kaggle platform

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Introduction

This document presents a general overview and concrete steps involved in running a code development competition on Google's data science and machine learning platform, Kaggle. This SOP is written for HuBMAP members and others who might be interested in organizing their own competitions on the platform to accelerate development of solutions for their problems by engaging a global community of experts and non-experts in the field of data science and machine learning.

Roles and Responsibilities

The **Competition Host** works to design the competition, specify the competition aims and expected outcomes, procures and curates the competition dataset, works with the Kaggle data scientists to finalize competition datasets and metrics, acquires sponsors for competition prizes, monitors and supports the competition for the duration of its run, validates the winning solutions, and potentially leads publication of the competition results in an academic journal.

The **Kaggle Lead** is the program manager at Kaggle that works with the Competition Host to oversee the organization of the competition on the platform, making certain it abides by the Kaggle rules, and leads the requisite legal contracts.

Subject Matter Expert (SME): An SME is a person with extensive knowledge about a given topic. In our case, SMEs lend their expertise to ensure that the proposed competition problem is feasible and the gold standard dataset is of the best possible quality.

Table 1. Roles, names, and email addresses of key personnel.

Role	Name	Email
Competition Host	Yashvardhan Jain Katy Börner	yashjain@iu.edu katy@iu.edu

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Kaggle Lead	various, assigned by Kaggle	
SME	various	

Procedures

Preparing for a competition:

- Ideate to ensure you have a feasible competition idea with a concrete machine learning problem and a clear goal.
- Collect and curate the relevant data for the competition, ensuring a decent amount of acquired data is unpublished and shall remain unpublished until the competition ends.
- Hold a preliminary meeting with the Kaggle Lead at this stage to get some initial input regarding feasibility, Kaggle rules, and potential competition launch timeline.
- Conduct a thorough analysis of the data, including input from Subject Matter Experts (SMEs), and test the feasibility of the proposed problem with the curated dataset.
- Sample the acquired data into a training set, public test set, and a private test set. The exact sampling is subject to change with input from the Kaggle Data Scientists at a later stage.
- Acquire the ground truth (gold standard) labels for your datasets, which will be used for training the machine learning models as well as testing them against a predefined metric. Depending on the dataset, problem, and available resources, this process can often take months. This may involve two stages:
 - manual (semi-automated) labeling of datasets (depending on the type of problem)
 - a final review and approval by a Subject Matter Expert (SME) to ensure best possible quality
- Secure the funds for the competition. Often, there will be a fee that Kaggle charges to provide the platform and compute for the competition. Depending on the type of competition, a certain amount of cash prize money may be involved. Both the Kaggle service fee and the minimum required prize money should be discussed with the Kaggle Lead as early as possible.
- Provide the final competition dataset to the Kaggle Lead for review by their data scientists. Ideally, this should be provided to Kaggle at least 3 months before the proposed competition launch. The final competition launch date is at Kaggle Lead's discretion.
- Conduct pilot data analysis, identify appropriate metrics and create a baseline model to test the competition feasibility and expectations. Kaggle has a suite of metrics that are mostly appropriate for most problems. For more specialized metrics, work with Kaggle Lead to identify the appropriate and practical metrics.
- Other than the cash prizes, the Competition Host can offer other prizes as well, such as authorship on papers, interviews for a job, presentation in conferences. While the

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primary cash prizes are based on performance on the leaderboard based on the metric, additional cash prizes can be offered based on team diversity, innovative solutions etc. These should be discussed with the Kaggle Lead early on.

- Secure contracts between Kaggle and Competition Host and complete payments. Award money and competition fee should be paid to Kaggle before competition launch.
- Launch competition.

During the competition

To ensure a successful competition do the following:

- Actively monitor the Discussion Forums and Public and Private Score Leaderboards.
- Respond to queries by teams participating in the competition.
- Work with Kaggle to ensure no rules are violated during the competition run and teams are not engaged in unfair practices.
- Competition concludes.

After competition concludes

With competition results in hand, perform the following tasks:

- Kaggle runs their anti-cheating algorithm, ensuring no Kaggle rules were broken and removing participants engaged in unfair practices such as using multiple accounts etc., and finalizes the leaderboard.
- Kaggle Lead shares results with the Competition Host.
- The winners are required to submit their solutions--including documentation, training and inference code, external datasets, trained models--to the Competition Host either via the Kaggle Portal or by sharing the files directly to the Competition Host via GitHub or similar platforms. Details depend on the data and code licenses used for the competition, and the rules set prior to competition launch.
- The Competition Host has the right to validate the solutions and ensure they match the leaderboard scores, although they reserve the right to skip this step. If any solution fails this validation for some reason, the next team on the leaderboard is assigned as the winner.
- Once the Competition Host finalizes the official winners, Kaggle Lead schedules winners' calls between the Competition Host and the winning teams where the teams present their methodologies to the Competition Host and the Competition Host gets the opportunity to interact with the teams and ask any questions regarding the methods and results. This can be a 1 hour per team call or a winners' panel as a 2 hour call with all winners.
- After the winners' call/panel and the Competition Host's approval, Kaggle releases the prize money to the winning teams.
- Optionally, the results of the competition are written up in a scholarly publication by the Competition Host.

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Note: The entire process can take up to a year and several steps run in parallel. While this is the general process, Kaggle is a private entity and may change rules and processes any time. The Host should contact the Kaggle Lead as early as possible and work with them closely to develop and run the competition.

References and Resources

The below references and resources were used in writing this Standard Operating Procedure.

1. Jain, Yashvardhan, Leah L. Godwin, Yingnan Ju, Naveksha Sood, Ellen M. Quardokus, Andreas Bueckle, Teri Longacre et al. "Segmentation of human functional tissue units in support of a Human Reference Atlas." *Communications Biology* 6, no. 1 (2023): 717. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-40291-0>
2. Jain, Yashvardhan, Leah L Godwin, Sripad Joshi, Shriya Mandarapu, Trang Le, Cecilia Lindskog, Emma Lundberg, and Katy Börner. 2023. "Segmenting Functional Tissue Units across Human Organs Using Community-Driven Development of Generalizable Machine Learning Algorithms." *Nature Communications* 14 (1). <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-023-40291-0> .

Glossary

Competition Dataset: The final dataset that is provided to the participating teams and is made available on the competition webpage of Kaggle's competition platform. The dataset comprises a publicly available training dataset, a public test set which is not directly available to the participating teams but is used to score their solutions which are visible to the participating teams, and a private test set which is not accessible, directly or indirectly, to the participating teams.

Competition Metric: A machine learning and/or data science metric used to score Kaggle competition solutions against gold standard dataset labels.

Private Leaderboard: The leaderboard used for the final rankings of a Kaggle competition, where teams are ranked on their final two selected entries. This leaderboard is not visible to the participating teams during the competition. It uses a private test dataset for calculating the scores.

Public Leaderboard: The leaderboard used for team rankings during a Kaggle competition based on their best scoring entry. This leaderboard is visible to the participating teams during the competition. It uses the public test dataset for calculating the scores.

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